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Biomimetic Esthetic Rehabilitation of Anterior Teeth: A Case Series

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Abstract

Anterior esthetic rehabilitation plays a pivotal role in restoring both function and confidence in patients with compromised anterior dentition. This case series illustrates a biomimetic approach to the restoration of anterior teeth using minimally invasive techniques and adhesive ceramic restorations. Through careful diagnosis, smile design, and systematic treatment planning, natural esthetics and harmony with the surrounding dentition were achieved, enhancing patient satisfaction and self-esteem.

Introduction

The anterior dentition plays a pivotal role in facial esthetics, phonetics, and psychological well being. Discoloration, spacing, malalignment, or developmental anomalies in the anterior region often affect a patient's smile and self confidence. Excessive anterior teeth display during smiling may potentially influence the self perceived psychosocial impacts of malocclusion in adolescents.^[1] Dental esthetics significantly affect a person's quality of life by shaping self perception, social behavior, and psychological well being.^[2]

Modern adhesive dentistry allows for conservative and biomimetic restorations that preserve tooth structure while achieving life-like esthetics. Biomimetic restorative approaches, combined with digital smile design, improved material science, and minimally invasive protocols, have made it possible to restore anterior teeth with excellent functional and esthetic outcomes.^[3]

Case Series

Case 1 – Indirect Technique Using Lithium Disilicate Veneers

A 29 year old female presented to the Department of Prosthodontics with a chief complaint of discoloration in the upper anterior teeth (Fig. 1 a, b). Clinical and radiographic examination revealed generalized

brownish intrinsic stains consistent with dental fluorosis, with intact enamel, healthy gingiva, and normal pulp. Oral prophylaxis was performed, and shade matching was completed using the VITA 3D-Master guide (A2 enamel). A silicone putty index was fabricated to guide minimal tooth preparation (Fig. 1 d). After preparation, an intraoral digital scan was obtained to capture tooth details and plan E-max veneer design for esthetic rehabilitation (Fig 1f).

Bonding Procedure: Teeth were etched for 20s using Smart Etch (ivoclar vivadent) followed by application of Universal adhesive (Ultradent) and light curing for 20 s. The E-max veneers were etched with 5% hydrofluoric acid (Porcelain Etch, Ultradent) for 20 s, treated with Silane coupling agent (Ultradent) for 1 minute, and luted using RelyX U200 resin cement (3M). Excess cement was removed, and each surface was light cured for 40 s to ensure optimal polymerization and bond strength.^[4,5]

Finishing and Outcome: Occlusal interferences were verified and adjusted, followed by final polishing using ceramic polishing kits (Diaceria/Optrafine, Ivoclar Vivadent). The E-max veneers (Ivoclar Vivadent) demonstrated excellent shade match, translucency, and marginal fit, with minimal tooth reduction. The patient was highly satisfied with the esthetic and functional outcome (Fig. 1 k, l).^[6,7]

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Figure 1: Case 1. (a) Prerehabilitative smile view, (b) Prerehabilitative frontal view, (c) Diagnostic wax-up, (d) Putty reduction guide index, (e) Incisal preparation with guide in situ, (f) Intraoral scan of preparation (g,h) Digital designing of the veneers with incisal overlap design, (i) Emax veneers on digital cast (j) Etching and silanization of the ceramic veneers (k) Final prosthesis in situ, (l) Postrehabilitative view, (m) Pre- and postrehabilitative smile view

Case Report 2 - Direct Veneers Using Injection Molding Technique

A 62 year old female patient reported to the Department of Prosthodontics with the chief complaint of yellowish discoloration of previously placed composite veneers on her upper front teeth. She desired replacement to improve esthetics.

Clinical examination revealed discolored, roughened composite veneers with no underlying caries or structural defects. Gingival health was satisfactory, and pulp sensibility tests were normal. Radiographs confirmed intact tooth structure and absence of pathology.

The old composite veneers were carefully removed, and the tooth surfaces were cleaned and polished. Shade selection was done using the VITA 3D Master guide (A2 enamel). A diagnostic wax-up was done on diagnostic cast, and an Exaclear index was made to accurately transfer the design intraorally.

Injection Molding Procedure: Teeth were isolated and etched using Smart Etch (Ivoclar Vivadent) for 20 seconds. The bonding agent (Ivoclar Vivadent), was applied and light-cured for 20 seconds (Fig f). Using the Exaclear (Ivoclar Vivadent) index, flowable composite EvoFlow (Ivoclar Vivadent), Shade A2 (Fig d,e) was injected to precisely recreate the planned morphology. The index was removed, and excess composite was carefully trimmed.

Finishing and Outcome: Final contouring and polishing were performed using multi-step polishing discs (Sof-Lex, 3M) to achieve a smooth, glossy surface. The injection-molded composite veneers provided excellent shade match, anatomical form, and surface finish. The patient was highly satisfied with the improved esthetics and natural smile appearance.

Limitation: Injection molded composite veneers are technique sensitive, prone to staining, and may have reduced longevity compared to porcelain veneers (Tzimas, K2025).^[8]

Figure 2: Case 2. (a) Prerehabilitative smile view, (b) Prerehabilitative intraoral view before and after removal of old composite restoration, (c) diagnostic wax-up, (d,e) EXACLEAR™ clear PVS material syringed onto a non-perforated mandibular tray to capture an accurate impression of the waxed up model (f) Selective enamel etch, one tooth at a time, with isolation using teflon (PTFE) tape to protect the adjacent teeth and bonding agent applied on tooth surface, (g) Injection moulding with flowable composite EvoFlow (Ivoclar Vivadent), (h) Final intraoral view, (i) Post rehabilitative extraoral view, (j) Pre- and post rehabilitative smile view

Case Report 3 – Resin Bonded Prosthesis

A 35 year old female patient reported to the Department of Prosthodontics with the chief complaint of a missing upper front tooth⁽¹¹⁾ following trauma, which had compromised her esthetics and smile.

Clinical examination revealed the absence of tooth 11, with healthy adjacent abutment teeth^(12 and 21) and adequate space for replacement. Gingival health was satisfactory, pulp sensibility tests of the abutments were normal, and radiographic evaluation showed good bone support without pathology.

Tooth Preparation: For resin bonded fixed partial dentures (RBFDPs), tooth reduction was kept performed on 12 and 21 which was confined to enamel: about 0.3–0.5 mm on the lingual surface, a shallow 0.3–0.5 mm chamfer with supragingival margin to create space for the retainers while preserving maximum enamel to enhance bonding strength. The incisal end of the tooth preparation was kept 1 mm cervical to the incisal edge.^[9]

Framework Fabrication: In resin bonded fixed dental prostheses fabricated with lithium disilicate (E-max), the retainers should be designed with a minimum thickness of 0.7–1.0 mm on the palatal surface to ensure sufficient strength and resistance to fracture while maintaining a conservative approach limited to enamel. The connector to the pontic should measure at least 4 × 4 mm (≈16 mm²) to resist functional stresses. This design achieves a balance between mechanical reliability and esthetics, since unlike metal retainers, ceramic retainers require slightly greater thickness for durability but still allow a minimally invasive preparation ideal for RBFDPs.^[10]

Bonding Procedure: The lithium disilicate retainer wings were etched with Porcelain Etch (5% HF, Ultradent) for 20 s, rinsed, dried, and treated with Silane (Ultradent). Abutment enamel was selectively etched with Smart Etch (35% phosphoric acid, Ultradent) for 20 s and bonded using 3M Universal Adhesive. The

prosthesis was luted with RelyX U200 resin cement (3M), excess cement removed, and light cured for 40s. This protocol ensures optimal bond strength for lithium disilicate resin bonded FDPs.^[11]

Finishing and Outcome: Occlusion was verified and adjusted, followed by polishing. The resin bonded FDP provided excellent esthetic integration, functional stability, and a minimally invasive replacement for the missing anterior tooth. The patient was highly satisfied with the natural result.

Figure 3: Case 3. (a) Prehabilitative smile view, (b) Prehabilitative intraoral view, (c) Prehabilitative intraoral occlusal view, (d) Cast after preparation, (e) Cast with prosthesis, (f) Buccal and palatal view of resin bonded restoration (g) Final intraoral view with prosthesis, (h) Post rehabilitative smile view

Discussion

Anterior esthetic rehabilitation is one of the most challenging aspects of restorative and prosthodontic dentistry because it requires restoration of both appearance and function while preserving the natural integrity of tooth structure. The cases presented in this series demonstrate that a biomimetic, adhesive, and minimally invasive approach can provide predictable, long-lasting, and natural looking outcomes. The biomimetic concept emphasizes conserving enamel to achieve reliable adhesive bonding and maintain the natural biomechanical properties of the tooth. Adhesive protocols have evolved substantially, allowing durable adhesion to enamel and dentin and eliminating the need for aggressive mechanical retention.

Lithium disilicate ceramics (E-max) were used for veneers and resin bonded fixed prostheses (RBFDPs) due to their high flexural strength, optical translucency, and long-term success rates. Several studies confirm the excellent longevity of lithium disilicate restorations, with survival rates above 95% after 10 years^[12]. In this case series, the E-max veneers effectively masked intrinsic discolorations associated with fluorosis, while maintaining translucency and marginal integrity. The RBFDP made of lithium disilicate served as a conservative solution for a single missing anterior tooth, providing esthetic harmony without extensive tooth reduction or biological compromise. These outcomes are consistent with previous clinical evidence showing the reliability of lithium disilicate RBFDPs in the anterior region over medium- to long-term follow-up periods.^[13]

The injection molding technique for direct composite veneers used in one of the cases provided a cost-effective and reversible option for smile enhancement. The use of a transparent silicone

(Exaclear) index derived from a diagnostic wax-up ensured accurate reproduction of tooth anatomy and controlled material placement. Although composites provide good esthetic results initially, their surface roughness and susceptibility to discoloration may reduce long-term performance compared to ceramics.^[14] Regular finishing and polishing are therefore essential for maintaining their gloss and longevity.

Digital workflows such as intraoral scanning, computer-aided design, and 3D printing have further improved the precision and predictability of anterior esthetic treatments. The digital approach minimizes human error, enhances the fit of ceramic restorations, and enables accurate visualization during planning. These technologies support the biomimetic concept by facilitating minimally invasive preparations guided by digital indices and by allowing direct communication between clinician, laboratory, and patient.^[15]

Overall, this case series reinforces that anterior esthetic rehabilitation can achieve natural harmony and long-term durability when based on conservative tooth preparation, appropriate material selection, and sound adhesive principles. Although technique sensitivity and maintenance requirements are limitations, the biological and esthetic benefits outweigh these challenges. The results confirm that adhesive, biomimetic restorations can restore not only the form and function of anterior teeth but also the patient's confidence and smile esthetics.

Conclusion

Conservative, adhesive based biomimetic restorations provide an effective and predictable approach for anterior esthetic rehabilitation. By integrating advanced ceramics, modern composite resins, and digital workflows, clinicians can achieve esthetic excellence while preserving maximum tooth structure. Lithium disilicate veneers offer superior long-term esthetics and strength for discolored or defective anterior teeth, injection-molded composite veneers serve as a minimally invasive and economical alternative for moderate corrections, and resin bonded fixed prostheses present a conservative option for replacing a single missing tooth. The key to success lies in precise diagnosis, careful planning, and strict adherence to adhesive protocols. Respecting biological limits, maintaining enamel preservation, and using materials that mimic natural enamel and dentin ensure restorations that are esthetically pleasing, functionally stable, and biologically sound. Biomimetic adhesive dentistry thus represents a paradigm shift from conventional mechanical retention toward a more conservative, functional, and lifelike esthetic restoration philosophy, embodying the future of modern restorative and prosthodontic practice.

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Heal Talk- Every healthy Smile deserves to Shine

